

Mind-Controlled Mobility Solutions Utilizing Electroencephalogram-Based Brain-Machine Interfaces

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Abstract:

This research project focuses on the innovative development of mind-controlled mobility solutions using electroencephalogram (EEG) signals through a non-invasive Brain-Machine Interface (BMI) to empower individuals with mobility impairments. By incorporating both synchronous and asynchronous Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) methodologies, this study aims to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of brain-controlled systems through the analysis of multiple brain signals to refine user intent interpretation for seamless control over mobility devices. A key aspect of the project is the implementation of shared control mechanisms to

enhance system security, enabling collaborative interaction between users and devices for safe and reliable operation. Machine learning classifiers, including support vector machines, artificial neural networks, and decision trees, has been evaluated for real-time processing of EEG signals to determine the most effective algorithms for translating brain activity into commands that facilitate essential movements like moving forward, backward, and turning. This systematic approach will involve signal acquisition, preprocessing, classifier training, and user testing to validate system efficacy. Ultimately, this project seeks to bridge the gap between neurotechnology and practical mobility applications, contributing valuable insights to neuroscience, engineering, and rehabilitation while enhancing the usability and accessibility of assistive devices to improve the quality of life for individuals with physical disabilities.

Keywords: *Assistive Technology, BCI, EEG, Learning Algorithm, Model Training, Motor, Imagery Prediction.*

Introduction

In Recent advancements in assistive technology have greatly improved the quality of life and independence for individuals with disabilities, especially in mobility solutions. Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) have emerged as a promising

area due to advancements in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and data processing and analytics. BCIs enable direct communication between the brain and external devices through electrodes.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have revolutionized multiple fields by delivering data-driven knowledge and enabling automation that were previously impossible. In agriculture, these technologies have made precision farming possible through automated systems capable of detecting weeds and diseases in the fields, enabling more efficient crop breeding and resource management (Shrestha et al., 2024). In autonomous systems, use of DL techniques for computer vision related tasks have allowed advanced driver assistance systems to improve further in safety and autonomy (Ojha et al., 2022). In medical domain, ML models have made breakthroughs in disease diagnosis, drug discovery, and personalized medicine possible by analyzing complex datasets. Various Machine learning and techniques and large language models (LLMs) are also being increasingly utilized to prepare datasets for biomedical applications. Advances in data processing and term extraction using LLMs (Chataut et al., 2024), have been pivotal in refining complex data interpretation, facilitating more precise annotations and insights. Similarly, transformer-based architectures have also shown notable potential in enhancing complex image segmentation tasks by combining contextual information with feature identification especially useful in analyzing microscopic images, a process relevant to high-precision (Gurung et al., 2023).

In addition, Non-invasive systems like Electroencephalography (EEG) stand out for their safety and ease of use. EEG-based technologies, which detect electrical brain activity through scalp electrodes, are particularly beneficial for individuals with neuromuscular disorders such as ALS or those recovering from strokes, where muscle-based systems like Electromyography (EMG) fall short.

However, EEG-based systems face challenges due to environmental interference and inconsistent performance. Security concerns about signal interpretation and limited validation on users with disabilities further hinder adoption. Most studies have been conducted on healthy subjects, raising questions about real-world reliability. Various applications systems

have been developed using EEG based BCI such as controlling the cursor on the monitor screen (J R Wolpaw et al., 1991), Combining Mu/Beta rhythms from motor imagery and P300 potentials offers a promising approach for enhancing accuracy and control in two-dimensional cursor navigation for EEG-based brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) (Yuanqing Li et al., 2008), Developed a new means of communication for the completely paralysed that uses slow cortical potentials (SCPs) of the electro-encephalogram to drive an electronic spelling device (N. Birbaumer et al., 1999), (Tanaka et al., 2005) developed a brain-controlled robotic wheelchair whose left or right turning movements are directly controlled by corresponding motion commands translated from user brain signals while imagining left or right limb movements, and tested this system in real-world situations. (Kyuwan Choi, 2005) also used a BCI based on motor imagery to build a brain-controlled mobile robot that can perform three motion commands including turning left and right and going forward and validating this robot in the real world. Jose del R. Millan (Jose del R. Millan et al., 2004) developed the first brain-controlled mobile robot in a virtual world using ERD/ERS BCIs. They induced ERD with the following mental tasks: relax, left-hand movement imagination, and right-hand movement imagination or cube rotation. (Rebsamen et al., 2006) first proposed to apply a P300 BCI to develop a brain-controlled robotic wheelchair. Many researchers have developed various brain-controlled robotic wheelchairs using a P300 BCI, since then. Since the BCI project using non-invasive devices is unstable and might act abnormal at times, it requires researchers to set up a test environment with all necessary precautions. Researchers have been using different test environments such as simulated conditions where both robots and environments are simulated (Tao Geng et al., 2010). Other than simulated conditions researchers have been using realistic conditions where both robots and environments are real. Xavier PERRIN (X. Perrin, 2009)²², (C. Mandel et al., 2009)²⁶. Since we aim to be efficient and reliable enough to be used in real life, we will use realistic conditions where robots and

environments are real. The system will be tested in people with different levels of brain status ranging from a healthy brain to a stroke brain. We want to propose a system with more security using multiple BCIs working together with shared control systems to improve both security and efficiency.

Our research aims to design a mind-controlled robotic system that enhances the security and accuracy of existing EEG-based systems. By integrating multiple brain signals and using robot intelligence, we seek to create a more stable and reliable assistive tool for individuals with neuromuscular disorders, improving mobility and quality of life.

Materials and Methods

The process initiates as the subject engages in specific cognitive tasks, during which brain activity is recorded using the Emotive Insight EEG device. The recorded EEG signals are then transmitted to a computer for pre-processing, where noise and artifacts are removed to enhance signal clarity. This preprocessed data is subsequently fed into a machine learning model that performs feature extraction. Based on the extracted features, the model generates a prediction, providing insight into the subject's cognitive state or task performance. Electroencephalography (EEG) signals can be transformed into control signals through the implementation of a Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), enabling users to command devices in their environment. EEG signals are captured using EEG headsets, which then relay the data to a computer for processing meaningful commands that facilitate device operation. Due to the inherently low amplitude of EEG activity, typically measured in microvolts (μV), these signals are susceptible to external stimuli and internal states, resulting in significant artifact contamination. The primary frequency bands of human EEG waves, which are critical for understanding brain activity, are outlined below (Figure 1).

In this study, we primarily focused on motor imagery tasks, necessitating the selection of a

specific frequency band for analysis. For effective motor imagery classification, we targeted the frequency range of 8–30 Hz, which encompasses both the Beta and Alpha frequency bands. This selection was made from a total of five frequency bands, allowing for enhanced signal processing and classification accuracy relevant to our research objectives.

Figure 1. Brain Waves and Their Associated Activities

Placement of Electrodes

The accurate placement of electrodes on the user's scalp is a critical aspect of EEG signal acquisition, as improper positioning can result in degraded signal quality. Typically, electrode placement follows the 10–20 international system, which standardizes the positioning of electrodes based on specific anatomical landmarks. In this system, electrodes are positioned at intervals of 10% and 20% of the measured distance from reference points, including the nasion, inion, and left and right preauricular sites. This systematic approach ensures optimal signal fidelity and reliability for subsequent analysis. It is important to note that the selection of electrode placement is contingent upon the specific type of brain signals being captured. This consideration is essential for optimizing signal acquisition and ensuring that the recorded data accurately reflects the underlying neural activity relevant to the research objectives.

Figure 2. EEG Signal Acquisition

We utilized a five-channel headset to acquire EEG data from five specific channels: AF3, AF4, T7, T8, and Pz, as illustrated in the connection diagram below.

Figure 3. Fitting the Headset

Proper positioning of the headset is essential for accurate EEG data acquisition. The frontal sensors should be aligned directly above each eye, positioned approximately three finger widths above the eyebrows. To ensure optimal contact between the sensors and the scalp, it may be necessary to re-moisten the sensor pads with a rehydration solution. This meticulous positioning and preparation are crucial for obtaining high-quality signals for subsequent analysis.

Connection

The device was paired via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), initiating the data streaming process. This connection method ensures low power consumption while maintaining a reliable transmission of EEG data for analysis.

Fitting the headset

Prior to fitting the headset, primer fluid from the sensor pack was applied to each of the five

sensors and both reference electrodes. The headset was then powered on, with confirmation that the white LED on the front was illuminated. Subsequently, the device was connected via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) or to a USB dongle before placing it on the subject's head. This preparation is critical for ensuring optimal sensor performance and data quality during EEG signal acquisition.

Obtaining good contact quality

As the Insight sensors establish and maintain contact, it may take a minute or so, for the signal quality to stabilize. If sensor indicators remain red or black, check that the sensors are making comfortable but firm contact with the scalp. If sensors indicate dark green, then we have obtained good contact quality.

Preparations were undertaken to train the subject for the acquisition of motor imagery EEG data in a controlled, soundproof

environment to minimize external noise and reduce artifacts. After establishing proper connections, the subject entered a baseline relaxation state, alternating between open and closed eyes, to create a stable reference point for subsequent motor imagery tasks. Training was conducted using the EmotivBCI platform, which facilitates the use of mental commands to optimize the generation of desired EEG signals for effective data acquisition and analysis. The protocol included a neutral state and up to four trained commands per profile, with integrated feedback mechanisms to refine command execution. A live cube demonstration offered an interactive platform for real-time testing and practice. Subjects were encouraged to closely follow instructions and engage in regular practice to enhance the effectiveness of their mental commands, focusing on techniques that yielded the best results for their individual performance.

Figure 4. Mental Training

During the training session, the subject was instructed to visualize specific mental commands as outlined, ensuring that no voluntary muscle movements were made. Each command was practiced for a minimum of five repetitions to promote proficiency. Emphasis was placed on maintaining extreme focus throughout the training process, as this concentration is critical for the accurate generation of EEG signals associated with the intended mental commands. EMOTIV offers six fundamental metrics of mental performance

that are derived directly from the user's mental activity. They are Engagement, Stress, Interest, Focus, Excitement, Relaxation. These measures provide valuable insights into cognitive function and engagement, enabling a comprehensive assessment of mental performance based on EEG data. Among these 6 mental performances, we are mainly focused on 'Focus'.

Figure 5. Different Mental pPformances

Training Environment and Subjects

The experiment was conducted with ten subjects in a controlled environment characterized by minimal noise. Prior to training, it was imperative to ensure good contact quality between the EEG headset sensors and the subjects' skin. Once the Insight device was paired, several guidelines were employed to facilitate optimal sensor contact. The two sensors on the black rubber reference arm were positioned to touch the skin behind the ear, with the arm bent as needed for proper placement. The forehead sensors were adjusted to make contact approximately three finger widths above the eyebrows or slightly lower. If a connection was established, the reference indicator changed from red to green, indicating that one or more sensors were functioning properly. The headset may have needed adjustments to ensure that the connections located on the inner face of the headset penetrated the hair; sweeping the hair aside or starting with slightly damp hair was beneficial. Additionally, the headband sensor was positioned under the hair to make contact with the scalp above the right ear. The rear sensor, often the most challenging to position,

required careful placement under the hair to find the scalp, which could be aided by parting the hair around the sensor with a comb. To enhance conductivity, a drop of contact lens fluid or saline, such as a simple saltwater solution, was applied above the sensor. A mixture of 80% glycerin and 20% saline solution could also be prepared for longer-lasting effects, with the fluid dripped onto the hair just above the sensor's location. Once contact was established, perspiration and the sensor's fluid would help maintain the connection throughout the experiment.

Figure 6. Obtaining Good Contact

After establishing optimal contact quality, the participants proceeded to the training session, where they were instructed to maintain a neutral mental state. Training was conducted using the EmotivBCI software provided by the Insight platform. The software offers a neutral state along with four motor imagery commands for training purposes. During the training, participants were required to visualize specific mental commands corresponding to the push, pull, and neutral states. The distance between the resulting data points for these commands indicated their distinguishability; greater separation between the data points correlated with improved performance and a higher probability of accurately classifying the mental commands. To achieve optimal performance, each command was practiced for a minimum of ten repetitions, ensuring that participants could generate consistent and recognizable EEG signals associated with each mental command. This rigorous training regimen was essential for

enhancing the effectiveness of the Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) in accurately interpreting mental activity.

Observations and Results

Not all individuals are able to maintain full focus and attention during specific tasks, which can negatively impact the quality and performance of training. This variability in concentration levels may lead to inconsistent data acquisition and reduced effectiveness of the training regimen, ultimately affecting the overall outcomes of the Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) training process. Addressing this issue is essential for optimizing training protocols and enhancing participant engagement to improve performance.

Following the training of each mental command for five repetitions, participants were assessed for their ability to effectively generate the desired EEG signals. This practice aimed to enhance familiarity and proficiency with the commands, thereby improving the overall accuracy and reliability of the Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) system in interpreting mental activity.

Table 1. Mental Commands after 5 Times

Participant No	Gender	Hair length	Contact quality	EEG quality	Training Result	Attention value	Differently -abled
1	male	short	Good	Good	Good	19	No
2	male	very short	Good	Good	good	45	No
3	male	long	No signal	bad	great	73	No
4	female	long	No signal	bad	poor	23	No
5	female	short	Good	Good	great	18	No
6	male	short	Good	Good	good	55	No
7	female	long	No signal	poor	bad	0	No
8	male	short	Good	Good	great	10	No
9	male	short	Good	Good	great	56	No
10	male	very short	Good	Good	Good	80	No

Among the ten participants, only 20% demonstrated an attention value exceeding 70, while 40% achieved a value greater than 50. These results indicate variability in attentional

engagement levels across the subjects, which may influence the effectiveness of the training and the subsequent performance of the Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) system.

After training each mental command for ten repetitions, participants were evaluated on their ability to consistently generate the desired EEG signals.

Table 2. Mental Commands after 10 Times

Participant No	Gender	Hair length	Contact quality	EEG quality	Training Result	Attention value	Differently-abled
1	male	short	Good	Good	Good	56	No
2	male	very short	Good	Good	good	67	No
3	male	long	No signal	bad	great	80	No
4	female	long	No signal	bad	poor	25	No
5	female	short	Good	Good	great	30	No
6	male	short	Good	Good	good	76	No
7	female	long	poor	poor	bad	45	No
8	male	short	Good	Good	great	89	No
9	male	short	Good	Good	great	87	No
10	male	very short	Good	Good	Good	80	No

After training each mental command for ten repetitions, it was observed that 50% of the subjects achieved an attention value exceeding 70, while 70% attained a value greater than 50. These findings suggest that increasing the number of training repetitions for each command positively correlates with improved performance and the acquisition of satisfactory attention values. Consequently, only data from participants who demonstrated proficient performance during the training sessions were retained for analysis, while those who did not meet the performance criteria were excluded from further evaluation. This approach ensures that the data collected for subsequent analysis reflects high-quality responses indicative of effective mental command execution. Following the training on mental commands involving cube movements, the next step involved assessing which participants demonstrated superior mental imagery performance. This prepared the research team to acquire real-time imagery data, which would be exported via the

Cortex API. This API, built on JSON and WebSocket, facilitates easy access from various programming languages and platforms. Prior to data acquisition, certain prerequisites were established. With a valid EmotivID, users could access basic data streams, including motion data, mental commands, facial expressions, performance metrics (low resolution at 0.1 Hz), frequency bands, contact quality, and battery level.

Overview of an API Flow

Before initiating data streaming from the Cortex API, several preparatory steps must be undertaken to ensure a seamless connection. First, users must log in to the EMOTIV Launcher using their EmotivID. Next, it is essential to incorporate the correct application ID, client ID, and client secret, which are generated from the account dashboard on the Emotiv website, into the application. Following this, the application should call the request access API to establish a connection with Cortex, with access needing to be accepted via the EMOTIV Launcher. Once access is granted, the EMOTIV brain wear headset should be connected either via USB dongle or Bluetooth. Subsequently, the application must call the queryHeadsets API to retrieve a list of available headsets, and then utilize the control device API to connect to the selected headset. After establishing the connection, the authorized API should be called to obtain a Cortex token, which is necessary for subsequent requests. Finally, the create session API must be invoked to initiate a new session, thereby preparing the system for BCI data streaming. These steps are crucial for ensuring effective data acquisition from the Cortex platform.

After successfully connecting the application to the Cortex service, the authentication procedure must be followed to ensure secure access. The first step is to call the getUserLogin API to verify if the user is already logged in through the EMOTIV Launcher. Next, the requestAccess API is called, prompting the user to approve the application for access to Cortex services. Once approval is granted, the final step is to call the authorize API to generate a Cortex token, which

is essential for subsequent API requests. If a valid token from a previous session exists and has not expired, it can be reused to streamline the authentication process. These steps are

crucial for ensuring secure communication with the Cortex service and facilitating reliable data acquisition for research.

Figure 7. Overview of API Flow

After establishing a session with the headset, the next step involves subscribing to one or more data streams, which provide real-time access to

EEG, motion data, and various metrics from Cortex. Once subscribed, Cortex continuously sends data sample objects. The process begins by

opening a session, followed by invoking the createRecord function to start recording. After the recording is complete, the data can be exported to a CSV or EDF file using exportRecord. However, real-world EEG data often contains artifacts and noise, which can negatively impact the performance of machine learning models. Therefore, effective data preprocessing is crucial. The preprocessing steps include importing raw data, applying a bandpass filter, inspecting electrodes and rejecting noisy channels, epoching the data, inspecting and rejecting noisy epochs, running independent component analysis (ICA) to eliminate noisy components, and saving the preprocessed data. For this study, we utilized raw EEG data from PhysioNet.org, focusing on data from Subject One in EDF format. The analysis was conducted using the MNE Python library, with necessary libraries imported before reading the .edf file using the read_raw_edf function.

Figure 8. Raw EEG Data

EEG signals were filtered using a frequency band of 7-30 Hz prior to the application of the independent component analysis (ICA) algorithm. The finite impulse response (FIR) filter parameters were designed to create a one-pass, zero-phase, non-causal bandpass filter using the windowed time-domain design method, specifically the firwin technique. A Hamming window was employed, achieving a passband ripple of 0.0194 and a stopband attenuation of 53 dB. The filter's specifications included a lower passband edge of 8.00 Hz, with a transition

bandwidth of 2.00 Hz, resulting in a -6 dB cutoff frequency at 7.00 Hz. The upper passband edge was set at 30.00 Hz, accompanied by an upper transition bandwidth of 7.50 Hz, which corresponds to a -6 dB cutoff frequency of 33.75 Hz. Overall, the filter length was determined to be 265 samples, equivalent to 1.656 seconds. We are now prepared to perform independent component analysis (ICA) on our EEG data. Upon reviewing the raw EEG recordings, we observed the presence of significant electrocardiogram (ECG) and electrooculogram (EOG) artifacts, which can be effectively removed using the ICA algorithm. It is important to note that many magnetoencephalography (MEG) and electroencephalography (EEG) signals, including biological artifacts, exhibit non-Gaussian characteristics. Consequently, principal component analysis (PCA)-based artifact rejection may be less effective at distinguishing the actual signal from noise sources. To address this challenge, MNE-Python facilitates the identification of artifacts and latent components through temporal ICA, enabling more precise artifact removal and improving data quality.

Figure 9. ICA Components

Figure 10. Topo Map of ICA Components

Next, the noisy components identified during the ICA process were excluded to enhance the signal quality. This step ensures that only the relevant EEG signals are retained, effectively reducing interference from artifacts and improving the dataset's integrity for subsequent analysis.

Figure 11. Signals

After data cleaning, the reconstructed EEG signals exhibited a notable reduction in spike artifacts, indicating improved data quality and consistency for further analysis. The denoised data was subsequently saved in a .edf file format, preserving the artifact-free signals for further analysis and ensuring compatibility with standard EEG data processing workflows.

Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is a critical component in the machine learning process, as selecting relevant features enhances model performance while extraneous data can increase computational demand and contribute to overfitting. Therefore, identifying and extracting key

features is essential. For this purpose, the EEG signal analysis library eeglib in Python was utilized, providing specialized tools and functions for effective EEG feature extraction. Finally, the power bands from different EEG channels, particularly the alpha and beta bands relevant to motor imagery tasks, were saved into a CSV file to facilitate future classification processes. This structured dataset serves as a foundation for subsequent analyses and model training.

bandPower_AF3_alpha	bandPower_AF3_beta	...	bandPower_F8_beta	bandPower_Pz_alpha	bandPower_Pz_beta
55.777713	236.030192	...	361.789831	74.879218	179.625799
67.017031	260.131282	...	317.279410	73.932460	197.634141
58.406914	211.538598	...	305.409846	89.492884	166.186895
59.344116	227.070420	...	305.955042	77.644315	151.666086
95.039128	310.543321	...	320.701187	83.474407	207.691141

Figure 12. Power Bands

Following feature extraction and data preparation, the dataset is now ready for training in the machine learning model. This stage marks the beginning of model training for classification and predictive analysis.

Machine Learning Algorithm

Various algorithms were evaluated based on accuracy and F1 score to determine the model best suited to the dataset. Specifically, four algorithms were considered in this project: Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA). The algorithm demonstrating optimal performance was selected for subsequent analysis.

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Naive Bayes scores:
F1_score: 0.565 (0.081)
Accuracy: 0.479 (0.044)
Decision Tree scores:
F1_score: 0.446 (0.040)
Accuracy: 0.450 (0.044)
SVM scores:
F1_score: 0.398 (0.090)
Accuracy: 0.479 (0.056)
LDA scores:
F1_score: 0.466 (0.070)
Accuracy: 0.496 (0.059)

```

Figure 13. Naive Bayes Scores

Following the evaluation, the Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) model was

selected for training and testing on the dataset, based on its superior performance metrics.

Figure 13. Correlation between Different Variables of Channel AF3

Upon analysis, a high correlation was observed between the delta, theta, and low alpha frequency bands. Consequently, the delta and theta variables were removed to optimize model performance and reduce redundancy.

Figure 13. After Reduction

Following dimensionality reduction, the remaining variables exhibited lower inter-correlation, enhancing the dataset's suitability for modeling. Despite this, the model demonstrated robust performance, even under conditions of reduced adherence to ideal

correlation constraints. In our study focusing on motor imagery EEG data, we identified the alpha (7–12 Hz) and beta (12–30 Hz) frequency bands as critical components during motor imagery tasks. Accordingly, we filtered the dataset to include only these power bands prior to model training. The dataset was then partitioned using the train-test split method from the scikit-learn library, with a test size of 0.33. Subsequently, we saved the trained model as "LDA_model.sav" for future predictions. To assess the model's performance, we employed the Repeated Stratified K-Fold cross-validation technique, resulting in an accuracy score of approximately 0.555. Our ongoing efforts are aimed at enhancing the accuracy of this model.

Concept of Shared Control

The concept of shared control addresses the challenges posed by the instability of non-invasive devices and user fatigue, which can lead to hazardous situations, particularly in robotics. In this framework, human operators and intelligent controllers collaborate to manage the system, with control responsibilities dynamically shifting based on specific circumstances. Shared control methods are divided into two categories: the first allows the human operator to maintain control most of the time, with the intelligent controller intervening in predefined situations like obstacle avoidance. The second group requires the user to specify a target location, while the intelligent controller navigates to that target, permitting the user to take control when necessary. Our research utilizes this second group of shared control strategies to enable seamless transitions between the intelligent controller and the human operator, thereby optimizing performance and safety in robotic applications.

Our project integrates several essential components to establish a robust navigation system, utilizing both hardware and software-assisted sensors. Cost-effective components, including ultrasonic and infrared (IR) sensors, along with cameras for image processing, contribute to the system's functionality. The navigation system employs three-phase inverters to regulate the Brushless DC (BLDC) motor,

utilizing Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) techniques governed by a microcontroller. The PWM signal facilitates precise motor control, while a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller assesses the error signal generated from the discrepancy between the measured speed and the desired speed. This error signal is subsequently utilized to compute the voltage required for motor command, ensuring accurate and responsive control of the navigation system.

Figure 13. Flowchart of Vehicle Algorithm

Figure 14. Flowchart of Prediction Script

Figure 15. Overall System Block Diagram

Figure 15. Project System Design

Figure 16. Overall Working Principle

Training Result

In our study involving the training of mental commands across ten participants, performance varied among subjects. One notable participant who exhibited commendable performance is identified as follows:

- **Name of Subject:** Kamal Thapa
- **Gender:** Male
- **Hair Length:** Short
- **Mental Commands:** Neutral, Push, and Pull
- **Attention Value:** 85

Figure 17. Training Results

Figure 18. Training Results in dotted format

Figure 19. Bot

PCB Designs

Figure 20. PCB Schematic

Discussion

This project titled "Mind-Controlled Mobility Solutions Utilizing Electroencephalogram-Based Brain-Machine Interfaces" represents a significant advancement in the field of neurotechnology and assistive devices, particularly in the context of enhancing mobility for individuals with disabilities. By integrating brain-machine interfaces (BMIs) with electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, this

research seeks to revolutionize the way assistive technologies can be controlled through mental commands. The ability to translate cognitive intent directly into actionable commands offers profound implications for improving the quality of life and independence of users who face mobility challenges. The significance of this project extends beyond its technical achievements; it addresses critical real-world issues faced by individuals with disabilities, such as limited mobility and the need for assistance in daily tasks. The research explores innovative human-robot interaction through shared control strategies, allowing for a dynamic interplay between human intention and robotic execution. This approach is particularly vital in rehabilitation and assistive robotics, where user engagement, adaptability, and responsiveness to user needs are paramount. By facilitating seamless transitions between user control and intelligent automation, the project holds the potential to enhance the effectiveness and user satisfaction of assistive devices. Moreover, the practical applications highlighted in this study encompass various domains, including healthcare, rehabilitation, and daily living assistance. The findings lay a solid foundation for future innovations aimed at addressing real-world challenges faced by individuals with disabilities, thereby contributing to a more inclusive society. The research also delves into the intricate aspects of EEG signal processing and classification, emphasizing the importance of employing robust algorithms capable of handling the continuous, non-linear, and non-Gaussian nature of EEG data. The effective use of techniques such as Independent Component Analysis (ICA) for denoising signals showcases the methodological rigor behind the project. In addition to its practical implications, the publication of this research contributes valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge in neuroscience, robotics, and human-computer interaction. By exploring the intersection of these interdisciplinary fields, the project serves as a critical reference point for subsequent studies, encouraging further exploration and development of BMI technologies. The collaborative nature of this project, which merges principles from neuroscience,

engineering, and computer science, underscores the importance of interdisciplinary approaches in driving technological advancements. Overall, the significance of this research lies in its potential to transform assistive technologies, enhance user autonomy, and improve the quality of life for individuals with disabilities. The article is not only worth reading for its innovative contributions but also for its implications for future research and development in the rapidly evolving fields of neurotechnology and robotics. This project exemplifies the potential of brain-machine interfaces to create meaningful change in the lives of those with mobility impairments, making it a valuable addition to academic literature and a beacon for future advancements in the field.

Conclusion

Our research focuses on the training of mental commands across various participants, with the objective of selecting individuals who demonstrate strong performance for subsequent real-time data retrieval. Given that EEG signals are continuous, non-linear, and non-Gaussian, a nonparametric algorithm is generally preferred for classification. However, in this project, we employed Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), a parametric algorithm that has proven to be robust and capable of yielding satisfactory accuracy even when these assumptions are violated. For the denoising of EEG signals, both Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Independent Component Analysis (ICA) are recognized for their effectiveness in artifact removal. While PCA is typically utilized for dimensionality reduction, ICA is employed to separate components by transforming the input space into a maximally independent basis. Given our goal of isolating distinct components from noise, we opted for ICA in our denoising process. Furthermore, we successfully operated the robotic system by integrating all components with a printed circuit board (PCB) and controlling the bot using code executed on a Raspberry Pi.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Birbaumer, N., et al. (1999). A spelling device for the paralyzed. *Nature*, 398(6725), 297–298. <https://doi.org/10.1038/18581>
- Chataut, S., Do, T., Gurung, B. D. S., Aryal, S., Khanal, A., Lushbough, C., & Gnimpieba, E. (2024). Comparative study of domain-driven terms extraction using large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.02330*.
- Choi, K. (2012). Control of a vehicle with EEG signals in real-time and system evaluation. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 112(2), 755–766. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-011-2029-6>
- Geng, T. G. J., & H. H. (2010). A self-paced online BCI for mobile robot control. *International Journal of Advanced Mechatronic Systems*, 2(1–2), 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJAMECHS.2010.030846>
- Gurung, B. D. S., Khanal, A., Hartman, T. W., Do, T., Chataut, S., Lushbough, C., & Gnimpieba, E. Z. (2023, December). Transformer in microbial image analysis: A comparative exploration of TransUNet, UNet, and DoubleUNet for SEM image segmentation. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM)* (pp. 4500–4502). IEEE.
- Li, Y., et al. (2010). An EEG-based BCI system for 2-D cursor control by combining Mu/Beta rhythm and P300 potential. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 57(10), 2495–2505. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2010.2055564>
- Mandel, C., Lüth, T., Laue, T., Röfer, T., Gräser, A., & Krieg-Brückner, B. (2009). Navigating a smart wheelchair with a brain-computer interface interpreting steady-state visual evoked potentials. In *Proceedings of the 2009 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems* (pp. 1118–1125). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS.2009.5354534>

Millan, J. R., Renkens, F., Mourino, J., & Gerstner, W. (2004). Noninvasive brain-actuated control of a mobile robot by human EEG. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 51(6), 1026–1033.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2004.827086>

Ojha, G., Poudel, D., Khanal, J., & Pokhrel, N. (2022). Design and analysis of computer vision techniques for object detection and recognition in ADAS. *Journal of Innovations in Engineering Education*, 5(1), 47–58.

Perrin, X. (2009). Semi-autonomous navigation of an assistive robot using low throughput interfaces. *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research*, 6(2), 62–66.

Rebsamen, L. C., Zhang, C., Zhang, Q., & Guo, B. (2006). A brain-controlled wheelchair based on P300 and path guidance. In *Proceedings of the First IEEE/RAS-EMBS International Conference on Biomedical Robotics and Biomechatronics* (pp. 1101–

1106). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BIOROB.2006.1639043>

Shrestha, S., Ojha, G., Sharma, G., Mainali, R., & Galvin, L. (2024). Automated grassweed detection in wheat cropping system: Current techniques and future scope. *Journal of Precision Agriculture*, 1(1), 19–37.

Tanaka, K., & Wheeler, K. M. (2005). Electroencephalogram-based control of an electric wheelchair. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 21(4), 762–766. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TRO.2004.842350>

Wolpaw, J. R., McFarland, D. J., Neat, G. W., & Forneris, C. A. (1991). An EEG-based brain-computer interface for cursor control. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, 78(3), 252–259. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694\(91\)90040-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694(91)90040-B)